

found to be 40 ml. of .1M ammonium metavanadate-glacial acetic acid mixture and 50 ml. of .006 M cobaltous chloride solution. Hence for the isolation of the compound in the solid state, the said amount of the reactants were taken in a beaker and stirred vigorously for at least three hours at a controlled temperature of 80° in a thermostat. It was then evaporated to crystallisation in a water bath and left in vacuum. Deep orange red crystals were isolated after 14 days. It was recrystallised from hot water. The complete analysis of the compound was done. No traces of nitrogen was found in the element estimation technique. (Found: Co, 5.15; V, 44.95; H, 1.36; calcd. for $H_2[H_2V_{10}O_{28}]6H_2O$: Co, 5.31; V, 45.17; H, 1.41%). The compound was found to be a free acid of the heteropoly anion $[H_2CoV_{10}O_{28}]^{2-}$, in comparison to that of its previous ammonium salt. The basicity of the compound was determined by titrating it in borax solution and was found to be 2. To know, if all the hydrogen atoms are equally ionizable under the same condition, the above titration was done conductimetrically⁷. The two distinct breaks in the graph clearly indicated that two hydrogen atoms are equally ionizable.

Determination of Apparent Molecular Weight :

The cryoscopic method as has been applied successfully by Alexander⁸ and by Thilo and Krüger⁹ for molecular weight determination of certain inorganic polyacids and polyphosphates etc., in water and molten sodium sulfate decahydrate, has also been applied here for the determination of the approximate molecular weights of the compounds in the same condition, i.e., in water and molten sodium sulphate decahydrate. This determination showed the molecular weight of the compound to be 1367 and 1075 for $(NH_4)_4[CoV_{10}O_{28}]18H_2O$ and $H_2[H_2CoV_{10}O_{28}]6H_2O$ respectively as compared with the calculated values 1413 and 1129.

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Spectrophotometric Study of Uranium(VI) with 2-Hydroxy-5'-Halo Chalcone Chelate

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PERUSAL of literature reveals that ortho-hydroxy chalcones of biological importance¹⁻³, due to the presence of α : β unsaturated carbonyl group (-OC-CH=CH-), exhibit the ability of chelate formation⁴⁻⁶. The efficiency of chalcones for the spectrophotometric investigations of various metal cations such as Be(II)⁵, Fe(III)⁶ and Ge(IV)⁷ has been observed.

In view of the analytical applications of chalcones the present investigations are aimed at to determine the composition and stability constant of uranium(VI) complexes with 2'-OH-5'-Cl (HCC), 2'-OH-5'-Br (HBC) and 2'-OH-4'-Me-5'-Cl (HMCC) which have not been studied so far. These reagents react instantaneously with uranyl ion and develop an orange colour. The chelates are highly stable and intensity of colour remains unchanged for a week.

Experimental

The solution of uranium (VI) was prepared by dissolving AnalaR uranyl nitrate in ethanol. The metal content was determined by the titrimetric method of Nadkarni et. al.⁹, which agreed with the gravimetric method¹⁰. 2'-OH-5'-Cl (HCC), m.p. 108°, prepared by the method of Keror, Yen and Reichstan¹¹ and 2'-OH-5'-Br (HBC), m.p. 107-103°, obtained by the method of Kostanecki and Ludwig¹². The 2'-OH-4'-Me-5'-Cl (HMCC), m.p. 141° was formed by usual method¹³. These chalcones were crystallized in ethanol.

Spectrophotometric measurements were done by using 'Bausch and Lomb' spectronic-20. All the observations were made at room temperature 25°.

Results and Discussion

Spectral curve : Absorbance spectra were recorded by mixing uranyl nitrate solution with reagent (HBC) in the ratio 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 against corresponding reagent-blank prepared under identical conditions. The maximum absorbance was found to occur at 435 nm showing the formation of only one complex. The same wave length was also found suitable in case of reagents (HCC) and (HMCC).

Effect of pH, time and temperature on the colour of the chelate :

Throughout the course of study the pH of the system was maintained 5.6 ± 0.2 as there was no change in the

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absorbance in this range. The colour formation has been found to be instantaneous and it was observed that even up to 120 hr, there was no change in the absorbance at room temperature. Order of the reagent addition was insignificant in the study. When the ligand is present in the excess the temperature change had very little effect on the colour formation. When the metal is in excess the intensity of the colour increases with an increase in temperature because of the accelerated interaction between metal ion and the reagent (HBC). Therefore, to maintain the constant condition the subsequent experiments were performed at room temperature (25°).

Adherence to Beer's law and optimum concentration :

Beer's law is valid up to 57.6 ppm of uranium (VI). The optimum concentration range for the effective photometric determination of uranium as evaluated by Ringbom's method¹⁴⁻¹⁵ is 17.7 to 31.6 ppm. The molar absorptivity calculated from Beer's law data is $2.51 \times 10^5 \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Effect of diverse ions :

The effect of ionic strength of the complex formation could not be investigated due to the lack of aqueous media in the study. However, ions like oxalate, citrate, fluoride, tartrate, beryllium and titanium ion interfere even in minute quantity, while nickel, manganese, copper, cobalt, palladium, chloride, bromide and iodide do not interfere.

Composition of complex in solution :

The molar composition of the chelate was established by three independent methods; the continuous method of Job's, the slope ratio method of Harvey and Mannings¹⁷ and mole ratio method of Yoe and Jones¹⁸. The results indicate that the formation of the complex between one mole of UO_2^{2+} and two moles of the ligand.

Evaluation of the stability constant :

The stability constant (K) has been calculated from the mole ratio method¹⁹. The value obtained of log K in the system uranium (VI)-2'-hydroxy-5'-bromo chalcone chelate, comes out to be 9.044 and the free energy of formation ΔF° , calculated by using the Van't Hoff Isotherm ($\Delta F^\circ = RT \ln K$) was found to be -12.33 cal/mole at 25°.

Entropy and Enthalpy changes :

In order to obtain the thermodynamic stability constant, the entropy and enthalpy were determined by Gibbs-Helmholz Equation at $\text{pH } 5.6 \pm 0.2$. The stability constant and free energy of formation of the chelate at five different temperatures are given in table-1.

TABLE 1—LOG K AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES, (pH=5.6)

Temp in °A	298	303	308	313	318
log K	9.0444	9.0611	9.0866	9.1657	9.2209
$-\Delta F^\circ$	12.3	12.5	12.8	13.1	13.4

The ΔH of the reaction was found to be -4.04 K cal/mole from the slope of the curve obtained by plotting log K vs $1/T$ (Fig. 1). Assuming this value of

Fig. 1

ΔH to be constant over the range of experimental temperature ΔS of the reaction has been calculated 54.9 e.u.

Structure of the complex :

The chromophoric group ($>\text{CO}$) is in conjugation with $\alpha : \beta$ unsaturated ($-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$), and phenolic group ($-\text{OH}$), leads to the resonating structure of the ligands. Further, the presence of halogen atom at the meta²⁰ position w.r.t. $\alpha : \beta$ unsaturated carbonyl group accounts for the intense colour of the stable complex with uranyl ion.

Assuming that the phenolic hydrogen is replaced by uranyl ion which in turn is coordinated through the carbonyl oxygen with the fact⁵ that the mole ratio between uranium (VI) and ligand (HBC) is 1 : 2. Thus the complexes may be represented by the general formula ML_2 .

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Cr(II), Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) Chelates of *o*-(N- α -furfuralideneimino) benzoic acid and 3-(N-2-furfuralideneimino) propionic acid.

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A perusal of the literature^{1,2} reveals that no systematic studies have been carried out on the bivalent metal chelates of *o*-(N- α -furfuralideneimino) benzoic acid (HFB) and 3-(N-2-furfuralideneimino) propionic acid (HFP) and hence the same was undertaken. HFB and HFP metal chelates were synthesised according to the literature procedure³.

Elemental analysis, molecular weight, magnetic moment, absorption and conductance data of the chelates are given in Table-1.

TABLE 1—MOLECULAR WEIGHTS, MAGNETIC MOMENTS, CONDUCTANCE, ABSORPTION DATA AND MOLAR EXTINCTION COEFFICIENT OF SOME BIVALENT CHELATES OF *o*-(N- α -FURFURALIDENEIMINO) BENZOIC ACID AND 3-(N-2-FURFURALIDENEIMINO) PROPIONIC ACID.

Composition	Molecular weight		μ_{eff} B. M. at 303°K	Λ M ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹	Absorption bands (cm ⁻¹)	Transition	Molar Extinction-Coeff (ϵ) mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
	Found	Calcd					
[CrL]	471	480	4.82	2.7	14300	⁶ E _g - ⁶ T _{2g}	44-50
[CrL']	(413)	(420)	(4.84)	(3.0)	(24800)		
[MnL]	475	483	5.91	3.2	24700	⁶ A _{1g} - ⁴ E _g (G)	54-71
[MnL']	(411)	(423)	(5.92)	(3.8)	(24800)		
					29900	⁶ A - ⁴ E _g (D)	68-86
					(30000)		
[FeL]	477	484	5.42	4.5	10200	⁶ T _{2g} - ⁶ E _g (D)	64-77
[FeL']	(413)	(424)	(5.44)	(4.4)	(10500)		
[CoL]	478	487	5.10	5.1	8400	⁴ T _{1g} (F) - ⁴ T _{2g} (F)	69-76
[CoL']	(416)	(427)	(5.12)	(5.3)	(8700)		
					16200	⁴ T _{1g} (F) - ⁴ A _{2g} (F)	89-91
					(16800)		
					20800	⁴ T _{1g} (F) - ⁴ T _{1g} (P)	96-102
					(21100)		
[NiL]	478	487	3.12	6.6	8700	⁶ A _{2g} (F) - ⁶ T _{2g} (F)	71-78
[NiL']	(417)	(427)	(3.14)	(6.8)	(9200)		
					13700	⁶ A _{2g} - ⁶ T _{1g} (F)	82-98
					(13900)		
					25600	⁶ A _{2g} - ⁶ T _{1g} (P)	99-110
					(26200)		
[CuL]	483	492	1.93	2.8	12800	⁶ E _g - ⁶ T _{2g}	122-132
[CuL']	(422)	(432)	(1.94)	(3.1)	(13300)		

where L=(C₁₁H₉NO₃)₂ and L'=(C₈H₁₀NO₄)₂

The values in parenthesis are those of the HFP chelates having the composition [(C₈H₁₀NO₄)₂M]. All the chelates gave satisfactory C, H, and N analysis.